

ANNUAL REPORT

1 APRIL 2018 – 31 MARCH 2019

**INTERNATIONAL ASTRONOMICAL UNION:
OFFICE OF ASTRONOMY FOR DEVELOPMENT**

Cover image: Sensory Solar System exhibit at the Galway Science & Technology Festival in Ireland. The exhibit was designed and produced by the OAD project 'Astronomy for All', as a tool for inclusive teaching of astronomy. (Image credits: Astronomy for All)

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INTRODUCTION

ABOUT US

Astronomy is a field that combines science and technology with inspiration and excitement. As such, it can play a pivotal role in facilitating education and human capital development. The skills related to the field of astronomy can also be used to further sustainable development throughout the world.

After the International Year of Astronomy (IYA) in 2009, the IAU was motivated to commit to more ambitious programmes of educating the world to the beauty of the universe and the sense of common humanity that derives from it.

The Office of Astronomy for Development (OAD) was established as a response to this renewed commitment. The OAD is a global office mandated to use astronomy to drive positive developmental change. It was established through a joint partnership between the International Astronomical Union (IAU) and the South African National Research Foundation (NRF).

After an international selection process, the IAU chose South

Africa as the host country for the OAD and the South African Astronomical Observatory (SAAO), a facility of the NRF, as the host institution. This arrangement was strongly supported by the South African Department of Science and Technology (DST). On the 16th of April 2011, the OAD was officially launched by then South African Minister of Science and Technology, Naledi Pandor, in Cape Town, South Africa.

The OAD engages in the pursuit of furthering the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) through its projects, partnerships, collaborations, and other astronomy-for-development activities.

“ASTRONOMY FOR A BETTER WORLD!”

The mission of the OAD is to use astronomy, including its practitioners, skills and infrastructures, as a tool for development by mobilizing the human and financial resources necessary in order to realize the field’s scientific, technological and cultural benefits to society.

PURPOSE

The OAD is a global coordinating centre for “astronomy-for-development”, tasked with coordinating relevant activities around the world as well as establishing and strategically coordinating Regional Offices and Language Expertise Centres. The vision of the OAD is “Astronomy for a better world”.

SCOPE

To use astronomy to stimulate global development, which is framed by the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals. As of 2019 the OAD has supported more than 140 “astronomy-for-development” projects reaching over 90 countries; established 10 regional offices around the world; and registered over 600 volunteers.

EXPECTED OUTPUTS

These are defined annually by the OAD Steering Committee. For the 2018 – 2019 financial year, the OAD largely focused on consolidating and optimising its initiatives including regional offices and projects; supporting the development and implementation of the next IAU Strategic Plan; building stronger links with the professional astronomy and other academic communities; and providing resources and capacity-building relevant to astronomy-for-development.

DURATION

This report covers the financial year from April 2018 to the end of March 2019. The current IAU-NRF agreement to host the OAD runs from the IAU General Assembly in 2015 until the IAU General Assembly in 2021. General Assemblies are usually held around August and take place every three years.

OVERVIEW

PARTNERSHIPS

Our philosophy is that the whole is greater than the sum of the parts. With key partners, the OAD can achieve its mission of using astronomy for a better world. Below are the partnerships which were active and/or established in the reporting period, from astronomy and space to social sciences. Visit our website for information on grants available through our partners.

INTER-UNIVERSITY CENTRE FOR ASTRONOMY AND ASTROPHYSICS (IUCAA), INDIA is one of the leading research institutes in astronomy/astrophysics globally. IUCAA also has a renowned programme of public outreach and education (SciPop). Since our establishment, OAD and IUCAA have enjoyed close ties. This partnership paves the way for specific collaborations in capacity development along with education, development and outreach.

SPACE GENERATION ADVISORY COUNCIL (SGAC) in support of the United Nations Programme on Space Applications is a global non-governmental, non-profit (US 501(c)3) organisation and network which aims to represent university students and young space professionals aged 18–35 to the United Nations, space agencies, industry, and academia. Both OAD and SGAC have common goals in strengthening global networks in space and astronomy and developing capacity in STEM fields.

The OAD has an ongoing partnership with the **RESEP GROUP (RESEARCH ON SOCIO-ECONOMIC POLICY)** in Stellenbosch University to take advantage of skills and expertise in development. RESEP has a long-term research focus on issues of poverty, income distribution, social mobility, economic development, and social policy.

ROYAL ASTRONOMICAL SOCIETY (RAS), UK encourages and promotes the study of astronomy, solar-system science, geophysics and closely related branches of science. The RAS and OAD have partnered to establish or nurture research, educational and/or development related collaborations between the UK and countries where astronomy research is not well established, specifically through a mobility programme.

DEVELOPMENT OF AFRICA THROUGH RADIO ASTRONOMY (DARA) is a joint UK–South Africa Newton funded project that uses radio astronomy training to develop high level technical skills in young graduates. The partnership is an implementation of the astronomy-for-development concept and involves collaboration at both strategy and project evaluation levels. In 2018, DARA funded four astronomy-for-development projects which were carried out by DARA participants in their countries of residence.

An MoU was signed with the **HUMAN SCIENCES RESEARCH COUNCIL** of South Africa for an initial planned school-based intervention.

REPORT

PUBLICATIONS

The work of the OAD was featured in several high profile articles during 2018–2019.

The first of these, titled "The potential of astronomy for socioeconomic development in Africa", was published as a comment in *Nature Astronomy*¹ and addressed the role of astronomy on a continent often defined through the lens of development challenges rather than science. The Portuguese Language Office of Astronomy for Development (PLOAD) published a comment in *Nature Astronomy*² highlighting the challenging work undertaken in networking the astronomy community, and embedding education and development through astronomy across the Lusophone world.

In conjunction with the launch of the MeerKAT telescope in July 2018, Dr. McBride published a piece in *The Conversation*³ to highlight that the investment in technology, as embodied by the MeerKAT project, has the potential for impact wider than the field of astronomy. Dr. Diaz-Merced published an article in *Four Seasons* magazine titled "The Sound of Stars" describing her work at the OAD.

¹ McBride et al. 2018, *Nature Astronomy* 2, 511–514

² Alves-Brito et al. 2019, *Nature Astronomy* 3, 366–368

³ www.theconversation.com/a-big-moment-for-africa-why-the-meerkat-and-astronomy-matter-99714

Portuguese-speaking countries. Member countries (blue) and potential/targeted partners (orange) of the PLOAD network are shown. Portuguese is the most widely spoken language in the Southern Hemisphere, with Brazil accounting for approximately 90% of the 240 million speakers in the lusophone community. Image is from the above article published in *Nature Astronomy*².

EVENTS

CONFERENCES & MEETINGS

The OAD staff participate in conferences and other meetings of strategic importance, reaching out to experts and practitioners in various disciplines in order to expand the OAD network, build collaborations and share knowledge.

Motivated by big data as a path to sustainable development goals and data as the common language for cross disciplinary interactions, the OAD participated in SciDataCon 2018, part of the International Data Week convened by CODATA, the ICSU World Data System and the Research Data Alliance. Dr. Vanessa McBride led OAD's session entitled "From Galaxies to the Global Goals: using data skills for development". The discussions focused on methodology transfer between astronomy and other sciences (e.g. medicine, economics) and various aspects of the structure of astronomy data, meta-data and skills transfer in the era of big data. She was also invited to talk at the "SKA-Driven Big Data Challenge in Africa: Science, Innovation and Opportunity" conference held in Madagascar.

The OAD was represented at the unveiling of the MeerKAT Radio Telescope in South Africa in July 2018, which was attended by

the Deputy President and several current and former Ministers. Further the OAD joined the SKA Africa Ministerial Meeting in Cape Town in October 2018. This was a gathering of Science Ministers and their delegations from the 9 SKA Africa partner countries. The OAD presented our work and the successful bid for the 2024 IAU General Assembly in Cape Town, the first time this assembly will be held in Africa.

Dr. Diaz-Merced traveled to Chile in October 2018 for a Bridging Event for Inspiring Stars, and the Meeting of Scientific Women Chile. She also traveled to the US in November 2018 for the Annual Biomedical Research Conference for Minority Students (ABRCMS) meeting and NASA 308 code presentation. Both trips were funded by her hosts. Later, she traveled to Europe for several events including: (i) the Bridging Event for Inspiring Stars

Dr. Vanessa McBride speaking at the OAD led session on "From Galaxies to the Global Goals: using data skills for development" at SciDataCon 2018 in Botswana.

at a Planetarium in Belgium; (ii) the Zero conference in Vienna; (iii) meetings at the United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs (UNOOSA) together with the IAU; (iv) astronomy class at Rabiccio correctional facility in Italy and, (v) the Italian Space Agency forum on equality and inclusion in space science.

Dr. McBride and OAD Director Kevin Govender attended a workshop, in October 2018, on the establishment of an optical observatory in Kenya, funded through the UK Global Challenges Research fund. The OAD is helping develop the case for the observatory in terms of societal benefits. McBride later attended a more detailed workshop in Kenya in February 2019 where she facilitated an interdisciplinary session exploring societal benefits of such an observatory. The OAD was also invited to participate in a meeting on Astro tourism, organised by the Department of Science and Technology and the Department of Environmental Affairs and Tourism in South Africa.

In November 2018, the OAD was invited to give a talk at the 2018 African Leadership Congress on space science and technology for sustainable development. This regional conference aims to promote cooperation among African countries in the use of space science and technology and was attended by stakeholders from space agencies and industry as well as a contingent of students and young professionals.

The office continued its contribution to the annual Science Forum

South Africa, where Dr. McBride joined a panel discussion on 'Science Communication for Policy Engagement'. A workshop on the African Open Science Platform, launched at the Science Forum, was later attended by Govender. This platform promises to change the landscape of science on the continent.

In January 2019, Govender joined the IAU Officers meeting by video. A month later, the OAD Steering Committee held its annual face-to-face meeting over 2 days at the OAD offices in Cape Town.

The OAD hosted an afternoon workshop for recipients of the Mandela-Rhodes Foundation Scholarship. The purpose of the workshop was to explore how these students from diverse fields could work together to contribute to a single global development challenge. Lessons from such events could serve useful in running similar workshops with an interdisciplinary audience. Driving collaboration across boundaries, the OAD participated in the "Dialogue between astronomers and social scientists" hosted by the Cosmopolitan Karoo research group at the University of Stellenbosch.

Venugopal attended two science communication conferences - Communicating Astronomy with the Public (CAP) conference held in Japan and Public Communication of Science & Technology held in New Zealand. These conferences afford an important opportunity to connect with communicators from various disciplines, who are working on challenges common across the globe.

The MeerKAT radio telescope in South Africa's Karoo region started gathering data in 2018, and is changing the way we see the universe. (Image: South African Radio Astronomy Observatory)

ACTIVITIES

SPECIAL PROJECTS & ACTIVITIES

In addition to the Annual Call for Proposals, the OAD undertakes, with the support of visiting experts, partners etc., and coordinates programmes with specific focus that align with the strategic objectives of the office.

ASTROSENSE

The AstroSense project, led by OAD postdoctoral research fellow, Dr. Wanda Diaz-Merced, aims to provide technology and didactic support for astronomy for those with different learning modalities, especially visual impairments.

During 2018/2019, Dr. Diaz-Merced worked with researchers from the University of Mendoza, Argentina, and supported the development of *SoundOne* – a tool for converting data into sound.

In 2018, the efforts of AstroSense blossomed into the Inspiring Stars project and exhibition. This exhibition was launched at the IAU General Assembly in Vienna in August 2018, and since then has become a key focus of the IAU's centenary celebrations under its *Inclusive Astronomy* theme.

At the end of March 2019, we sadly bid farewell to Dr. Diaz-Merced at the end of her post-doctoral fellowship. She takes up a position at the same location as the OAD's sister office – the Office for Astronomy Outreach – at the National Astronomical Observatory of Japan. She continues to sustain her work on the AstroSense project at her new home.

ASTRONOMY AT HBUs

One of the legacies of apartheid in South Africa is a very unequal, public, tertiary education system. "Historically black universities" (HBUs) generally focus on agricultural and/or applied sciences with less scope for curiosity driven science like astronomy, compared to wealthier universities in South Africa.

In recent years, through training of postgraduate students and individual champions at the HBUs, astronomy has been taking root in some of these campuses. And across other countries in the African continent, the injection of funding through big infrastructure projects, like the Square Kilometre Array, has given rise to an interest in astronomy.

As part of its project funding, the OAD has supported a number of activities that aim to develop astronomy teaching tools at university level, specifically targeted at places where there is little infrastructure or funding. These include

the projects - Starlight in the University Lab (2013, 2014), Starlight (Astrolab) Extended (2016) and Astrolab tutors and consolidation (2018, 2019), all led by Profs. Michele Gerbaldi and JP de Greve. These projects build on each other to provide observing time on remote telescopes, tutorial guides and training tutors to run and analyse observations of a variable star as a physics laboratory practical. The OAD has further supported development of astronomy at some of these institutes through training workshops.

The University of Zululand is now in the accreditation process for an undergraduate astronomy curriculum, and is selecting a site for a small optical teaching telescope (see image below) in a rural part of South Africa, along the lines of one of the OAD Flagship projects. The lessons learned through this process will be widely applicable to resource-scarce universities hoping to use astronomy as a gateway subject to introduce students to science and technology, and have the potential to be rolled out through the ten Regional Offices of the OAD.

FROM ASTRONOMY TO DEVELOPMENT

Tawanda Chingozha is a PhD student in development economics at Stellenbosch University and an OAD Fellow. He is leading the project on *Classifying the informal economy using satellite imagery*.

The informal sector, also known as the shadow economy, is the lifeblood of many developing countries. The sector provides a source of employment for the poor, many of them rural migrants in search of better opportunities – thereby contributing to national income. Against this background, the informal sector is unrecognised and 'illegal' by definition. Thus, it is notoriously hard to measure. A collaboration between astronomers and development economists is now exploring new ways of measuring and understanding the economic contribution from the informal sector in Zimbabwe.

A cross-disciplinary conversation between the Economics Department at Stellenbosch University, South Africa and the OAD led to the idea of using crowd sourcing as a way to explore the informal economy of Zimbabwe. Zooniverse is a citizen science platform that grew out of the need for astronomers to classify tens of thousands of galaxies detected in the Sloan Digital Sky Survey. The platform served images

of these galaxies to anyone with an internet connection, and after a short introductory tutorial, one was in a position to classify their first galaxies. In the last decade, the platform has expanded in capability and transcended disciplines to host research projects ranging from the arts to medicine, at the same time allowing professionals and volunteers to work side-by-side.

The project that emerged out of these conversations is called "A Citizen Science Approach to Classifying the Informal Economy using Satellite Imagery". In the project's pilot phase, participants are asked to view satellite imagery of Harare, Zimbabwe, and identify warehouses/structures of informal and formal trade; as well as informal vs formal housing.

The pilot takes advantage of the 2005 clean-up campaign in Zimbabwe to evaluate whether volunteers can detect informality changes and whether classifying a given satellite image many times increases accuracy. Results are valuable in enabling a comparison to be made between machine learning and citizen science in so far as informality classification is concerned. Overall, the project aids in creating the foundation upon which a first dataset on informality can be created not only for Harare, but other urban areas in Zimbabwe and beyond.

In February 2019, Dr. Diaz-Merced arranged a trip to the SAAO observatory in Sutherland for learners from Athlone School for the Blind and Pioneer School for the Blind. Several resources were developed for this activity that could be used for learners and members of the public with visual disabilities. She also participated in activities during her travels in the first quarter including presentations at Camps in Iowa and Michigan in the US and online with Astronomers Without Borders; presentation at Universidad Metropolitana in San Juan, Puerto Rico; visits to 24 schools in Puerto Rico, which resulted in the Department of Education signing an MOU to give workshops to 60 teachers on using astronomy in the classroom. Prof. Kathy Eastwood worked with Diaz-Merced on the CARDIS didactic tool to change from Cartesian to spherical coordinates, vector mapping and basic geometry concepts. This is a tactile tool to help teach these topics to blind students.

Dr. McBride coordinated the Royal Astronomical Society (RAS)-OAD call for grants, as part of the RAS-OAD partnership. Five recipients were selected who will be provided mobility funding for travel from or to the UK to nurture research, educational or development related astronomy collaborations. She also participated in the review and selection of DARA development proposals (in conjunction with Leeds University) in SKA Africa partner countries. This followed a workshop she ran in May 2018 for DARA students on how to design astronomy-for-development projects.

Through our partnership with IUCAA in India, a search tool has been developed for resources on astronomy for development. The beta version of the tool was revealed at the IAU General Assembly

in Vienna in August 2018.

The IAU issued an open call for proposals for seed funding for projects related to the IAU100 celebrations. Venugopal represented the OAD on the review panel. Govender serves on the oversight committee for IAU100.

Dr. McBride's academic links continue to be strong – the first quarter saw her PhD student receive the green light for his doctorate, as well as the conclusion of her teaching of the NASSP MSc Time Series Analysis and Data Analysis course (Feb - June 2018). She again taught this course in 2019. In October she traveled to the Netherlands and met with Silvia Toonen to start a new project on population synthesis to link radio pulsars and X-ray binaries.

The OAD was called upon to assist in the development of a plan for the re-launch of the African Astronomical Society (AfAS). Several meetings were held, with a larger meeting taking place 25-26 March 2019. This meeting was funded by the DST, hosted at SAAO, and organised by the OAD, had over 80 participants from over 20 countries (image below). The OAD facilitated discussions in the meeting which ended with the adoption of a constitution for AfAS and the election of an Executive Committee.

Thanks to the leadership of volunteer Jane Choi, and the past contributions of Eli Grant, the OAD released its first online course in July 2018. This is targeted at potential project proposers and aims to deliver content based on the lessons learned from OAD projects through the years.

EVENT

IAU GENERAL ASSEMBLY 2018

The 30th IAU General Assembly (GA), held from 20–31 August 2018 in Vienna, Austria, was the biggest astronomy event on the OAD calendar. More than 400 participants registered for OAD's Focus Meeting 15 (FM15) on Astronomy for Development which was held over 6 sessions between Tuesday 28th August and Friday 31st August 2018.

FM15: Astronomy for Development comprised a series of invited and contributed talks, panel discussions, two poster sessions, and a brain-storming session. In particular the meeting aimed to bring together science communicators, experts from development and science policy backgrounds, and astronomers in the various Divisions of the International Astronomical Union. A key theme of FM15, and of the 30th IAU General Assembly in a broader sense, was the pronounced inclusion of astronomy for development in the strategic plan. This is articulated as Goal #3 in the newly ratified IAU

Strategic Plan 2020–30: "The IAU promotes the use of astronomy as a tool for development in every country". It became clear through the submissions to FM15 that the landscape of astronomy for development is evolving rapidly. While the astronomy community has converged on a shared understanding of development where the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals are central, we are cognisant that "development" itself is a fluid concept, being rapidly redefined at global, regional and domain-specific levels.

EXHIBITION SPACE

The OAD shared an exhibition space at the General Assembly with the IAU Office for Astronomy Outreach (OAO), IAU100 anniversary, and the IAU Inspiring Stars inclusive exhibition. The centre piece of the exhibition was a 1.5 m diameter Earth ball that showed the extent of the IAU network and its activities including OAD funded projects, OAO outreach coordinators, and translator-volunteers. For 2 weeks, the IAU offices interacted with the 3000+ participants at the GA.

IAU100 ANNIVERSARY

2019 marks the 100th anniversary of the founding of the International Astronomical Union. The IAU has planned a year-long celebration to increase awareness of a century of astronomical discoveries as well as to support and improve the use of astronomy as a tool for education, development and diplomacy under the central theme "Under One Sky". IAU100 celebrations were officially launched at a special session at the General Assembly in Vienna.

INSPIRING STARS

The "Inspiring Stars" exhibition was launched at the IAU General Assembly. It is an itinerant, international exhibition to highlight initiatives that address the concept of "inclusion" in (but not limited to) outreach, didactic, and professional aspects using astronomy. It is a collaboration between the IAU Secretariat, the IAU Office of Astronomy for Development, and the IAU Office for Astronomy Outreach, with the support of the American Astronomical Society (AAS).

MEETINGS

In addition to FM15, the OAD participated in a number of meetings at the General Assembly such as the Young Astronomers Lunch, Division Day meetings, OAD Regional Offices meeting, OAO's Focus Meeting on global astronomy outreach, Focus Meeting on Global Coordination of International Astrophysics and Heliophysics Activities, Symposium S346 etc.

Sze-leung Cheung, then International Outreach Coordinator at the IAU Office for Astronomy Outreach, talking to local school children in Vienna about the work of the IAU. (Image: IAU OAD)

MAP

REGIONAL OFFICES

ACTIVITIES

REGIONAL OFFICES

Regional Nodes and Language Expertise Centres (ROAD/LOAD) are offices based around the world with similar objectives as the OAD but with regional focus. These offices work closely with the OAD in order to implement the IAU Strategic Plan. "Regions" which they focus on could be geographical (neighbouring countries) or cultural (language or cultural similarities spread over a large geographic region). The offices carry out various activities to disseminate astronomy knowledge, build human capacity, and advance research in order to use astronomy for development. Below are a selection of their activities in this period. Visit the OAD website for the entire list of activities.

ANDEAN REGIONAL OFFICE

- The Third Workshop *Astronomia en los Andes* was held from November 12–16, 2018 in Lima, Peru.

ARAB WORLD REGIONAL OFFICE AND LANGUAGE EXPERTISE CENTRE

- The 12th Arab Conference on Astronomy and Space Science was organized in Amman, Jordan from May 1–3, 2018.
- Weekly lectures were held at the Jordanian Astronomical Society's Cultural Forum in collaboration with Arab Union for Astronomy and Space Sciences under the umbrella of the Arab-ROAD.
- United Nations/Jordan Workshop on Global Partnership in Space Exploration and Innovation was organized by the Regional Centre for Space Science and Technology Education for Western Asia (RCSSTE-WA) & the United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs (UNOOSA).
- An agreement was signed between two of the OAD's regional offices (South West and Central Asian ROAD and the Arab World ROAD/Arabic LOAD). This sets out an example for inter-office collaborations which operate virtually independently of the OAD.

EAST ASIAN REGIONAL OFFICE AND CHINESE LANGUAGE EXPERTISE CENTRE

- Initiation and initial recording of the "Mars Colonization" multi-episode fictional documentary. The goal is to make the audience think about the future of humanity, the environmental problems on Earth, and the challenges associated with interplanetary space travel and colonization of a new planet. This was organized in collaboration with SINA Media, the Chinese Gemini Observatory, and the local government of Dunhuang in northwestern Gansu province, China.

- Ongoing projects include university-level astronomy development in Sichuan Province (China West Normal University; specialization in astronomy education and outreach) and Guizhou Province (Qiannan Normal University for Nationalities; specialization in radio and engineering).

EAST AFRICAN REGIONAL OFFICE

- First NASE (Network for Astronomy School Education) teachers training was held in Addis Ababa, organized by East African ROAD, Ethiopian Space Science & Technology Institute (ESSTI), and Ethiopian Space Science Society (ESSS).
- The office organized the Inspiring Stars Exhibition and Inclusion Workshop at Kotebe Metropolitan University (KMU) in collaboration with IAU-Inspiring star flagship program coordinator Dr. Wanda Diaz (OAD), KMU, ESSTI and ESSS.
- East African ROAD participated in the 14th General Assembly of the Ethiopian Space Science Society and the 1st ESSTI African Initiative for Planetary and Space Sciences (AFIPS) International Workshop.

EUROPEAN REGIONAL OFFICE

- The European Regional Office was launched during a regional workshop on astronomy for development, which took place at the European Week of Astronomy and Space Science in the UK.
- Kick-off of Space.Eu project at the University of Leiden in December. The project aims to use the excitement of space to encourage youth to choose careers in science and technology.

PORTUGUESE LANGUAGE EXPERTISE CENTRE

- ➔ Launch of the 100th Anniversary of Eddington@Sundy website, one of the programs under IAU100 celebrations.
- ➔ The fourth edition of Dia das Meninas no Museu de Astronomia e Ciências Afins (Girls' Day at the Museum of Astronomy and Related Sciences) in Rio de Janeiro took place under the theme "Diversity in Science", addressing gender and ethnic-racial issues, essential factors to achieve the Development Goals proposed by the United Nations.
- ➔ Brasil, Cape-Verde, Portugal and São Tomé and Príncipe organized lunar eclipse observations on 27 July 2018.
- ➔ World Science Day for Peace and Development on November 10 was celebrated with astronomy hands-on activities for more than 100 students in Cape Verde.

SOUTH EAST ASIAN REGIONAL OFFICE

- ➔ The 10th South East Asian Astronomy Network (SEAAN) 2018 Meeting was held from 19–21 October 2018 in Indonesia with 100 researchers and students from ASEAN Countries.
- ➔ NARIT-RUPP Human Capacity Training in Astronomy for Development 2018 was held 6–7 December 2018 at the Royal University of Phnom Penh (RUPP), the Kingdom of Cambodia with 80 RUPP Students majoring in Physics and Geography.
- ➔ NARIT organized a number of training schools and workshops as the UNESCO International Training Centre in Astronomy.

SOUTH WEST & CENTRAL ASIAN REGIONAL OFFICE

- ➔ IAU South West and Central Asian (SWCA) 2nd Regional Workshop was organized with participation of

representatives from Armenia, Georgia, Iran, Kazakhstan, Tajikistan and Turkey.

- ➔ Public lecture was given by Areg Mickaelian at Yerevan Phys-Math School "Astronomy in the World and in Armenia", gifting Celestron 11cm telescope to the school.

SOUTHERN AFRICAN REGIONAL OFFICE

- ➔ A training workshop for Astrolab Tutors was held from 18–22 June 2018 at the University of Zululand in South Africa.
- ➔ Mauritius hosted the 2nd African Space Generation Workshop from 17–18 December 2018 for students and young professionals.
- ➔ A Workshop on Planetary Sciences was held in Botswana from 28–31 October 2018, just before the International Data Week in Botswana from 5–8 November 2018.

WEST AFRICAN REGIONAL OFFICE

- ➔ A Science Communication and Astronomy Outreach Workshop was held from October 12–14, 2018 for a group of ten DARA students at Ghana Space Science and Technology Institute.
- ➔ The 7th African Leadership Conference on Space Science for Sustainable Development was held in Nigeria to discuss the implementation of the African Space Policy And Strategy.
- ➔ The Ghana Dish Conversion Workshop was held Jan 21–25, 2019, the first of a series of four workshops to be held in the year as being a part of the Development Through Radio Astronomy Global Network collaboration.

PROJECTS

FLAGSHIP THEMES

Background: Part of the OAD's strategy is to coordinate global "Flagship" or "Signature" projects, which would be implemented on a much larger scale than those funded through the annual call for proposals.

Flagships are seen as an effective means for achieving significant impact of astronomy for development over a substantial part of the world. The OAD has identified five flagship themes that encapsulate the idea of astronomy for development, and which have the potential for global roll-out. The selection of these

themes was based on the experience gained from supporting 140+ projects (and reviewing about 1000 proposals) since 2013, the input from 10 regional offices around the world, as well as special OAD projects, partnerships, international trends, etc.

THEMES: The five themes of astronomy-for-development that emerged from a consultative and review process are:

**KNOWLEDGE & SKILLS
FROM ASTRONOMY**

**TECHNOLOGY
FROM ASTRONOMY**

**STIMULATING
ECONOMIES**

**ADDRESSING
INEQUALITY**

**SCIENCE
DIPLOMACY**

In 2016, OAD funded a project in Indonesia that looked at creating benefits for a rural community surrounding the site of a proposed astronomy observatory. (Image: Community Development around Timor Observatory project)

OVERVIEW

FLAGSHIP PROJECTS

Following discussions with the OAD Steering Committee in February 2019, it was decided that there should be an initial focus on two of these themes. Subsequently the OAD has developed these ideas further into the following two flagship projects:

SUSTAINABLE, LOCAL SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT THROUGH ASTRONOMY

Building on the lessons, experiences and resources from several OAD projects over the years, this flagship aims to use an astronomical facility, such as an observatory or planetarium, as a "hub" within a small town or village to stimulate various associated socio-economic benefits for the local community. Depending on the local landscape and an initial needs assessment, benefits could include job creation through astronomy-related tourism, community skills development, educational programmes, stimulation of local innovation, alternative activities for youth in order to keep

away from negative/harmful activities, and infrastructure development. The establishment of such a facility in close collaboration with relevant government, industry, academic and development partners, including local and traditional leadership, will ensure the sustainability of the initiative. Once the model is developed, any number of implementations can be rolled out across the world, depending on availability of resources and competent project leaders or champions. This model can also serve existing large observatories as the concepts developed will certainly be relevant to them.

SCIENCE DIPLOMACY THROUGH ASTRONOMY: CELEBRATING OUR COMMON HUMANITY

Astronomy brings us a perspective of the beauty and scale of the universe. Most famously, astronomer Carl Sagan used this perspective to try to positively influence how people interact with their fellow human beings and our planet, through his description of the earth as a "Pale Blue Dot". This project aims to take the inspiring potential of astronomy and use it to stimulate a sense of tolerance and common humanity in all parts of the world. By partnering with relevant organisations, the project can develop guidelines, consolidate best practices, conduct relevant research and provide training, both online and in person, and thus enhance existing efforts for social cohesion.

Due to the nature of this project, it is important to clarify the difference between outreach and development. Outreach entails providing access to astronomical information while development aims at addressing specific UN Sustainable Development Goals. While there may well be overlaps, this project falls specifically under the latter and will not seek to promote astronomy but to use aspects of astronomy to achieve development goals.

The OAD funded project Columba Hypatia: Astronomy for peace uses astronomy to bring together children from both sides of the post-conflict island of Cyprus and promote a feeling of global citizenship. (Image: Columba/Galileomobile)

School children working together to assemble a Galileoscope during the 2019 Girls Astronomy Camp project in Nigeria. The project, which uses astronomy to inspire and educate girls to pursue STEM, has been funded twice by the OAD with support from Astronomers Without Borders (AWB), Nigerian Defence Space Administration and others. (Image: AWB Nigeria)

OVERVIEW

OAD PROJECTS

Every year, the OAD solicits ideas that apply astronomy in various ways to create positive impact on society. Proposals are invited from anyone, anywhere in the world regardless of background in astronomy. In fact, interdisciplinary teams are encouraged, especially team members and partners with development expertise/experience. The next call for proposals will be announced in April 2020.

“ASTRONOMY FOR DEVELOPMENT IS CENTRED AROUND PEOPLE RATHER THAN STARS.”

PROJECTS FUNDED IN 2019

The seventh annual call for proposals resulted in the selection of 20 projects which are addressing various challenges around the globe using astronomy. They are (in no particular order):

- 01 2019 GIRLS ASTRONOMY CAMP, Nigeria
- 02 AMANAR: UNDER THE SAME SKY, TARGETING SAHRAWI REFUGEE CAMPS near Tindouf, Algeria
- 03 AMAZONAS: CELEBRATING ASTRONOMY, Brazil
- 04 ASTROLAB: THE CONSOLIDATION PHASE, Southern, Eastern and West African countries
- 05 ASTRONOMY FOR CANADIAN INDIGENOUS PEOPLE, Canada
- 06 THE SUPERNOVA FOUNDATION MENTORING PROGRAMME, developing countries
- 07 ASTRONOMY TO DEVELOP PRE-ALGEBRA SKILLS, Uganda
- 08 MOLO MHLABA, South Africa
- 09 CLEAR SKIES, India
- 10 UNDER THE SAME SKY: TEACHING THE TEACHERS, Liberia
- 11 TEACHER TRAINING OUTREACH FOR ASTRONOMY AND SCIENCE, Mongolia
- 12 DEVELOPMENT THROUGH ASTRONOMY, Pakistan
- 13 FOURTH ArAS SCHOOL FOR ASTROPHYSICS, Arab league countries
- 14 INTERNALLY DISPLACED CHILDREN ASTRONOMY OUTREACH, Nigeria
- 15 INDONESIA MALAYSIA PROJECT ON ASTRONOMY EDUCATION USING TACTILE IMAGES, Indonesia and Malaysia
- 16 INDUSTRY SKILLS FROM ASTRONOMY FOR EMERGING ECONOMIES, South Africa
- 17 REACH FOR THE STARS (PLANETARIUM FOR THE BLIND), Philippines
- 18 SYSTEM SOUNDS: INTERACTIVE SPACE MUSIC, Canada and global audience via internet
- 19 THE 3RD SOUTH WEST AND CENTRAL ASIAN REGIONAL WORKSHOP for SWCA ROAD countries: Armenia, Georgia, Iran, Kazakhstan, Tajikistan, Turkey
- 20 BEHOLD THE SKY, Brazil

The OAD has also compiled a 'Recommended list' of projects that were approved by the reviewers but could not be funded due to our limited resources. Read the list of 'Recommended Projects' at www.astro4dev.org/2019-recommended-projects and contact us to support any of these projects.

PROJECT HIGHLIGHTS

Some of the highlights from OAD projects during the past year. For regular updates, follow us on social media: Facebook (www.facebook.com/astro4dev) and Twitter (www.twitter.com/Astro4Dev) or visit our website.

COLUMBA HYPATIA: ASTRONOMY FOR PEACE WON FALLING WALLS AWARD

Dr. Francesca Fragkoudi, PI of OAD project *Columba Hypatia: Astronomy for Peace* won the Falling Walls Engage science engagement award in 2018. The Columba Hypatia project, that takes place on the island of Cyprus, uses astronomy as a tool for promoting meaningful communication and a **culture of peace and non-violence**. It is led by GalileoMobile and the Association for Historical Dialogue & Research.

SCIENCE IN THE CITY OF GOD

Ad Astra Academy brings the excitement of exploration to students in poor regions of the world. Twenty children from Rio de Janeiro's City of God favela were trained, via a hands-on curriculum, to develop reasoning skills and learn about astronomy (image below). The students got an opportunity to explore Mars using **actual data from NASA's Curiosity rover** and interact with scientists at the NASA Jet Propulsion Laboratory. 'The Mars Academy', a documentary based on the project, was screened at the Borrego Springs Film Festival.

ASTRONOMY DAY FOR GIRLS

In February, the *Molo Mhlaba* project in South Africa celebrated the UN International Day of Women & Girls in Science and the IAU Women and Girls in Astronomy Day. Women astronomers and students conducted a day of activities with school children. **NASA astronaut Dr. Ellen S. Baker** visited the school on the day and spoke to students about her trips to space.

IAU 100TH ANNIVERSARY

As part of the *100th anniversary celebrations* of the IAU, 3 projects previously funded by the OAD have been selected for further expansion.

- Columba-Hypatia: Astronomy for Peace, Cyprus
- Astro tourism in Armenia and neighbouring countries
- Astronomy apps challenge in Gaza

PROJECTS REACH AND IMPACT

Since 2013, the OAD has granted €741,125 to more than 140 projects around the world through its annual call for proposals. This section reports the summary of the effect/impact of these projects on global development. This analysis was done during the 2018–19 financial year, at the request of the OAD Steering Committee.

GLOBAL FOOTPRINT

The OAD has funded and coordinated a total of 141 projects on 5 continents since 2013. These projects have used astronomy/space related topics to tackle challenges in their communities and regions in order to promote sustainable development and create a better society.

OAD projects have targeted various audiences – students, general public, policy makers etc. – in more than 90 countries around the world. The map below shows the countries targeted by projects between 2013–19. These include the location of projects as well as the origin of participants in the projects.

The above map was created using Microsoft Bing data. Country borders depicted are demonstrative and do not necessarily reflect the opinion of the OAD.

GRANT AMOUNT BY PROJECT

GRANTS AWARDED

A total of €741,125 has been awarded between 2013 and 2019 through the call for proposals. The IAU OAD call is meant for small to medium projects with the average grant amount hovering around €5000. These grants aim to encourage and kick start innovative ideas which fall outside the scope of traditional funding instruments. Projects are highly encouraged to look for matching or supporting funding from local institutions and other international bodies. External funding adds to the credibility and

stability of the project apart from ensuring sustainability. Projects funded in 2019, for example, have so far managed to raise €22,239 in external funds, leveraging the OAD grant.

Analysis of the grant funding reveals that just about 90% of projects received grants up to €8000. Only 3 projects were granted more than €10,000 in funding.

NASA astronaut Dr. Ellen Baker talks about her spaceflight experience to girls at the Molo Mhlaba school in Khayelitsha in Cape Town, South Africa. (Image: OAD)

IMPACT ON SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS

The OAD uses the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) as the framework for development. An analysis of OAD projects reveals that they have influenced at least 11 out of the 17 SDGs.

Every OAD project influences multiple SDGs but a majority of projects are linked to SDG 4: Quality Education.

ANALYSIS OF IMPLEMENTATION OF OAD PROJECTS

Completed projects were rated on how well they executed their plan and achieved their deliverables. A scale was used to score them, from 1 (least successful) to 5 (most successful implementation).

Projects in the graph are represented by their abbreviations
Size of circle = size of grant

Scale

- 1 incomplete data (project did not submit documentation)
- 2 low
- 3 average
- 4 very good
- 5 excellent
- 0 project cancelled

ANALYSIS OF IMPACT OF OAD PROJECTS

This second graph presents the impact of projects on development. The analysis, with input from a development economist, took into account factors such as positive outcomes from the project, sustainability of activities, project reporting and resources developed, influence on SDGs etc. Projects were scored on a scale of 1 (lowest impact) to 5 (highest impact).

Majority of projects have an impact score of 3 or above. The additional visualizations show the impact scores by various regions

Projects in the graph are represented by their abbreviations
 Size of circle = size of grant
 *two projects that were granted funding were unable to be implemented by the project teams. These "cancelled" projects are marked (in red) with an impact score of 0.

PEOPLE

OAD TEAM

The OAD has a small but effective team complemented by a number of visitors (interns, volunteers, fellows, researchers) who contribute on various projects. In addition, the OAD is served by a volunteer panel of reviewers (who evaluate the annual call for proposals) as well as a Steering Committee and further supported by a global network of 10 Regional Offices. The OAD is also dependent on operational support from various departments at SAAO, its host institution.

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MAX MOLARO
VOLUNTEER

REPORT

FINANCIAL INFORMATION

The OAD receives its operational funds from the IAU and the South African DST (through the NRF). The IAU also allocates around €110,000 every year for project grants.

The OAD operates within the financial systems and policies of the NRF, which comply with South African national legislation. The office receives an annual baseline income from the DST and the IAU, all administered through the NRF. The DST provides R1,500,000 per year (with a 6% annual increase) and the IAU provides an annual fixed amount of €70,000 as baseline income, as well as project funding of at least €110,000 per year. The DST additionally funds a full time Astronomer (with associated costs), and the IAU additionally funds a part time fund raiser.

million, with contributions from the IAU, DST, research grants and carry over from the previous year. Expenses amounted to around R3.4 million, with major expenses being salaries, office expenses, travel, workshops and conferences.

The main reason for the underspend has been unfilled staff positions since 2017. These funds have been directed towards OAD Flagship projects and are budgeted to be spent by the end of the current IAU-NRF agreement (August 2021).

In the 2018-19 financial year, the OAD's total income was R5.05

Income 2018/19

- IAU (€70,000 p.a.)
- DST (R1.5m+6% p.a.; R1m staff costs)
- Other income (projects and research grants)
- Carryover of operating expenses
- IAU Project funding (€110,000)

Expenditure 2018/19

- Staff expenses (salaries, fellows, consultants, recruitment, training)
- Office expenses (infrastructure and general running costs)
- Subsistence and Travel
- Workshops and conferences
- Production, printing and distribution
- OAD Special Projects
- IAU Project Grants (€113,100)

Breakdown of finances for the financial year 2018/19. Contact us for further details.

REPORT

SUMMARY FOR 2018–2019

The OAD received a boost at the IAU GA in August 2018 with a significant presence established both physically at the GA, and in the newly ratified IAU decadal strategic plan for 2020–2030. The OAD remains in a healthy, stable position in terms of funding and human resources., thanks to the excellent OAD staff as well as numerous volunteers, interns and fellows that have been serving the OAD. The current priorities are primarily:

- to give special attention to the development and implementation of “flagship” projects and associated fundraising campaigns,
- to implement the OAD call for proposals process for 2019,
- to consolidate the regional offices through self-assessments and reviews,
- and to continue to explore interdisciplinary partnerships to enhance the use of astronomy for development.

More information on the OAD activities can be found on the OAD website www.astro4dev.org.

In 2019, the OAD funded project 'Astronomy for Himalayan Livelihood Creation' launched its first Astro-Homestay, which welcome tourists to stay in the house of local villagers and experience the amazing night skies from trained women in the village. (Image: AHLC project)

**OFFICE OF ASTRONOMY
FOR DEVELOPMENT**

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